

THE ROLE OF ASSESSMENT IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR ESL STUDENTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6502555>

Urinova Shohsanam Nosirjon qizi

Teacher national University of Uzbekistan

Named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Abstract. *It is undeniable that assessment is a crucial part of teaching which cannot be ignored in any way. Assessment has a vital effect on the education process to inform and encourage ongoing learning, plays a crucial role (Cowie&Bell, (1999). This thesis looks at the most effective's ways of assessment as long as the ways to assess correctly based on certain principles.*

Key words: *Practicality, reliability, validity, washback, authenticity.*

Assessments are divided into two main categories which are called summative and formative assessment. These 2 types of assessment both define weaknesses and strengths of learning process and give actual score simultaneously. According to Pierce, assessment is a crucial part of any learning and teaching activity. It not only informs instructional decisions made on a day to day basis and helps diagnose student strengths and weaknesses related to classroom instruction, but also provide specific feedback to students in support of their learning. Moreover, assessment is, on the whole, very crucial parts of teaching, by this means, educators can determine the level of skills or knowledge of students (Taras,2005). It can be seen from the above mentioned ideas, both summative and formative assessment are equally important in teaching process and they determine either to what extent learners achieved the expected results or how they are making progress by evaluating their overall performance. Irfan Tosuncuoglu (2018) claims that by using appropriate assessments in the classroom, teachers will be able to both test and grade their learners, as well as can make their students notify about how well they do the assessment and , of course, they will determine and improve their teaching methods respectively according to this. Actually, language tests are varied for making decisions; therefore they are divided into 5 groups: achievement, placement, diagnostic, proficiency and aptitude tests. It is true that formative assessment is concerned as a vital one, which assists the teacher to investigate whether learning process is going well, the objectives are being achieved or not. Teacher can make changes in lesson plan or activities during the process itself by conducting formative assessment. Therefore, it is very helpful type of the test for the teacher to facilitate the learning process. While reporting on the importance of different types of tests and assessment, summative assessment type cannot be excluded from the list, as the result of its necessity. This is a

very important test type to make sure about success of the course and learner's achievement. They help us how to assess, test and evaluate learners successfully by considering all aspects. All in all, in my test modification project, I would like to explore one type of test used in local schools. Following this, I will be reporting a new version showing how I modified it based on 5 assessment principles.

The learner chosen for the project is a 16- year old schoolgirl whose name is Munisa. Currently, she is studying at school on grade 9th. Although the young learner came from Uzbek family, she knows the Russian language in a proficient way. The reason is her grandparents mainly use this language at home while communicating with their grandchildren. So her family is bilingual one where two languages are spoken at the same time. As for her educational background, she has been learning the English language on and off for 4 years. Therefore, her level is pre-intermediate. Due to the fact that the teaching system is not so well-developed in local schools, she is attending extra courses with a view to improving her skills in one of the learning centers in Andijon. When it comes to her learning style, it would probably be visual learner as she learns best whenever she watches and observes something closely. As for a type of learner, she is a dependent learner who feels more confident whenever she learns the language with partners. She learns best in pair and group works and gets bored when she studies autonomously. Despite the fact that she attends extra courses, there are still some areas she is lagging behind which should be improved. She has difficulty mainly in her productive skills, speaking, although her grammar and lexical resource are quite satisfactory, ideas never come her easily due to the lack of practice. Concerning with her writing, she has problems with her spelling and not aware of writing structures that are used in different types of essays and reports. Munisa has a strong wish to upgrade her skills and take CEFR exam the level she is intending for is B2.

The education setting the chosen learner, Munisa studies at school N 53 which is situated in Andijon region. The school where she studies uses a textbook called Fly High which is intended to improve pupils' all four skills. The books offer a wide range of activities, grammar exercises and reading/listening tasks to assess learners' performance on the English language. The education course called Andijon Development Centre, where she goes in order to get extra course mainly uses 'Headway' during the classes. It is well structured textbook that serves to develop learners' all four skills and sub-skills simultaneously. There is also an assessment part in this book to check learners' overall performance which is so helpful to check if learners are making progress or not.

ORIGINAL ASSESSMENT TEST.

The latest assessment test that was conducted at school to 9th grade pupils was the-end-of-term test which consists of 2 parts – dictation and grammar test. Dictation is a type of assessment in which the teacher dictates intended passage and pupils write

whatever they hear. The actual number of grammar test is 20 which were taken from the grammar topics in textbook. For both types of tests one hour and fifteen minutes were allocated. The assessment test was evaluated in the following scale. If learners make mistakes ranging 1-5, it will be marked 5 or if it would be 6-12, that would be 4. If the number of errors exceed from 12, the dictation marked 3. When it comes to grammar test, 2 points were given to each correct answer. If the candidate finds all answers right, it would probably be 40 points overall. Actually, Pupils were informed about the test before the test taking day so that they can be aware of the allocated time that would be spent on the test as well as the venue where the test was going to be carried out.

According to Brown (2004), with a view to making an assessment more effective, beneficial, valid and appropriate, the test takers must construct, structure and organize the assessment questions in a way that accurately coincides with cardinal criterion. Brown defines 5 fundamental types of criteria for testing a test: practicality, reliability, validity, authenticity, and washback. The testing system was well developed at school. Teachers tried to create tests based on the topics from the textbook and they made an effort to make it more practical. However, there are still some areas which should be improved. I'm about to analyze the test from each criteria relying on 5 essential types of assessment by Brown. Although the cost of the test was not so expensive and quite affordable, the Practicality of it failed due to the fact that students could not accomplish the task on time. This happened because of teachers' irresponsibility. They did not prepare enough handouts for each pupil. As a result some pupils had to start the test later than expected which had negative impact on their performance as well. However, the teachers were able to check all the answers within the given appropriate time and the results were announced even earlier than it was expected. In terms of reliability, pupils were provided with no rubric or assessment. Even there is not any kind of rubric for dictation. Dictation is more subjective process than some other forms of assessment (Brown, 2004). One question was still unanswered that according to which criteria, pupils will be assessed. It is right that in terms of test, holistic rubric was utilized but there was no any kind of analytical rubric that let pupils know about the reasons behind each score. Besides that as it were only multiple-choice questions and has only 3 options and some tests are not so well structured and therefore, it was easy to guess. The items need to be evenly difficult, distractors need to be well designed (J.D.Brown 2007). This made it so unreliable Furthermore, validity wise, although some questions were related to the topic, some of them were irrelevant and out of topic. The test does not check learners' all four skills. It focused on only writing and grammar and other skills of students were not taken into account. On the other hand, it provided meaningful and useful information on the topic. The extent to which inferences made from assessment results are appropriate, meaningful, and useful in terms of the purpose of the

assessment (Gronlund, 1998). Authenticity – the language used in the test was so natural as it was not taken from real-life situations. According to Chun (2006), many test types fail to stimulate real world tasks. Concerning with washback, it was more summative than formative and did not provide any feedback which made it so unclear, especially on dictation.

Overall, the summative assessment was well-structured in terms of writing and grammar. However, it seems to be so unrealistic only 2 skills are tested while the textbook covers all four skills. Actually, pupils practice reading, listening, speaking and writing at the same time during the lessons but when it comes to assessment, their only 2 skills are evaluated. This seems to be so illogical. Therefore, while modifying my test version, I tried to include all skills including speaking and listening. Viewing assessment from language performance, listening and speaking are very closely interrelated, which means that it seems almost impossible to isolate one from the other. Speaking activities involve directly the interaction of the aural comprehension, (Brown, D. 2003). So as all of them should be checked equally. The modified version of the test was intended to check learners' all skills and it lasted 1 hour and 30 minutes and it consisted of five major sections:

1. Listening – 10 questions – 10 minutes
2. Reading – 10 questions – 15 minutes
3. Speaking – 5 questions – 10 minutes
4. Grammar – 20 questions – 20 minutes
5. Writing – ESSAY on advantages and disadvantage of the internet– 35 minutes

The modified version of the test was intended to check learners' all skills and it lasted 1 hour and 10 minutes. While accomplishing this task, I heavily relied on the 5 principles suggested by Brown (2003). This is how I have changed the current test to make it more effective and reliable. In terms of Practicality, the test involved clear directions and instructions in each part. As the numbers of questions were not so many, pupils were able to do that on time as well as trainers who were able to check them within appropriate time limit. A test should be easy to design, easy to administer, easy to mark and easy to interpret the results (Bachman and Palmer, 1996). As for Reliability, there is a rubric on speaking and writing and the teacher gives explanation after each task explaining the reasons behind each score. All tasks were related to the topic given in the topic even though it was not exactly given in the book. So it checked a real knowledge of learners. The careful specification of analytical scoring instrument, however, can rise both inter-and intra-rater reliability (J.D.Brown, 1991). Concerning with Validity, it offers meaningful and useful information about test takers four skills and measured exactly what it intended. When it comes to Authenticity, it was natural as possible. What made it so spontaneous is the listening test that was taken from real-life situations. What is more, the assessment part also includes a

speaking test where pupils were required to answer to the questions randomly. In terms of Washback, as I have mentioned above, analytical rubric was used with the help of which pupils could be provided with feedback. So this time, it was more formative than summative. The washback effect may refer to both the promotion and the inhibition of learning (Messick, 1996).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion assessment is an integral part of teaching than cannot be ignored. A well developed assessment requires having a thorough study and research before applying it. While choosing any type of assessment, we should consider this from five principle perspectives suggested by J.D. Brown. We should keep it in mind that assessment has an impact on learning, especially on learners. With the help of appropriate assessment, learners can get to know their weak and strong points. Besides that teachers can evaluate their own teaching process and identify whether their students are making progress or not which helps them to choose right materials and change their methods, in a sense. Most importantly, above all, assessment should be aimed at improving learners' skills regardless of its types, whether it is summative or formative. All in all, assessment can be defined as the systematic and ongoing method of analyzing and using information from measured outcomes to improve student learning in terms of knowledge, acquired knowledge, understanding developed, skills and competences gained. Teaching and assessment should be coincided with each other as assessment usually evaluates what is learnt and acquired.

REFERENCE:

1. Brown, H. D. (2000). Principles of language learning and teaching. White Plains, NY: Longman. Duff, Patricia (2014) Case Study Research on Language Assessment Annual Review of Applied Linguistics, LTD
2. Ellis, R. (2005). Principles of instructed language assessment. Asian EFL Journal
3. Brown, H. Douglas (2004). Language assessment: Principles and classroom practices. White Plains, NY: Pearson Education.
4. Irfan Tosuncuoglu (2018). Importance of assessment in ELT university in Turkey.
5. Jose Pepe Perez (2019) Evaluating and assessing the four skills, university In Indonesia.
6. NJ Anderson, D Nunan (2008) Practical English language teaching: Reading - McGraw-Hill ESL/ELT
7. Racheal Roberts, Antonia Clare, JJ Wilson (2011). New Total English Pearson Education Limited. p. 36.